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**Agricultural and Environmental Data Science—
Interdisciplinary Field for the Sustainable Management—*An Overview***

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural Science and Information Science combine and make a subject called Agricultural Informatics and it is dedicated in developing and enhancing not only agricultural systems but also in environmental systems. It is dedicated in enhancing productivity, growth, pre-production activities, post-production aspect of the agriculture and so on. In enhancing agricultural practice Agricultural Informatics is worthy. Data is an important aspects and applicable in different sectors such as Healthcare sector, Government sector, Business, horticulture, Management, Education, Agriculture, etc. and for proper management of the data, various techniques are being used and Managing large amounts of data, Complex data management Big Data Management is important one. Agricultural Data Science can be considered as Big Data applications in Agriculture sector particularly viz. Efficient Agriculture Systems, Expansion of the Agro Systems, Speedy Agricultural Systems, Quality Production, Quantity Enhancement of Agro Products, Livestock Management. Environmental Data Science is the combination of the Environmental Science and Data Science. Internationally universities are moving towards newer and interdisciplinary programs and research; and in this context Agricultural and Environmental Data Science can be a perfect area for complete and sustainable development. This paper is talks about the aspects of Agricultural and Environmental Data Science with reference to sustainable development.

Keywords

Agricultural Data Science, Big Data, Agricultural Informatics, Ecological Data Science, Sustainable Agriculture, Environmental Information Science

Introduction

Objective

Agricultural Data Science

Data is important and applicable everywhere whether it is Healthcare sector, Government sector, Private or public sector, horticulture, Management, Education etc. apart from the Agriculture. Due to the growing amount of data in various activities and therefore various techniques are used for the scientific Data Management. The Big Data evolved as a Managing large amount of data and similar amount of facet and it is also useful in Complex data management; therefore it is called as Big Data Management. Here different analytical tools are also used and therefore it is also called as Data Analytics or Analytics. The applications of the Analytics for other areas created other

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domains and fields viz.—

- Business Analytics
- Healthcare Analytics
- Medical Analytics
- Marketing Analytics
- Government Analytics
- Learning Analytics etc.

As far as Analytics application in Agriculture is concerned, in short it is called as Agricultural Analytics. The term bigdata was emerged in the year 1990 but in last few years massive changes are noticeable due to the commercialization of data and also wider uses in different organization and institutes worldwide. In the year 1984 by the ‘Tera Data Corporation’ begun with the concept and gradually new shape formed; thereafter ‘Teradata’ have been used for several structured and unstructured data for proper and healthy data management. Another organization called seisent IMC also contributed lot in early days for big data and for the data collection and management. Thereafter Google, apache, Oracle, IBM, EMC, DELL etc. also played a leading role in Big Data and Analytics.

Big Data is gaining and is rising not only in the business and also in other areas and it is increasing day by day in other areas. The size is increasing tremendously from few dozen terabytes to many Exabytes even from 2012 to present 2020. Big Data and its characteristics are also changing radically—

- Big Data is needs healthy and better integration of data with diverse nature, complexity and also in massive scale.
- Big Data deals is close with data sciences nomenclature. It is very close with the software and high level of programming like Python or R programming language etc.
- It is also connected with the mathematical science and few intelligent science areas like artificial intelligence including machine learning, deep learning etc.
- This field is close with the parallel computing for a large number of data therefore operation research also important here.
- The business application of IT (that is business intelligence is also an important part of Big Data).
- Big Data lies on discrete mathematics, fuzzy logic, and descriptive mathematics.
- Big Data uses an inductive statistic for low information density.

Big Data: Basic Functions and Roles

Big Data is an important gatekeeper in Knowledge society and valuable for the managing data and responsible for various aspects such as—

- Mining Data from the Database and Data Warehouse or similar systems within a time

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frame.

- Big Data is responsible for the reducing of the complexity of data using technology and also management tools and technique.
- Big data is dedicated in managing large amount of data and in different sectors effectively.

Big Data is important and worthy in every sectors and therefore different other areas have been emerged viz. Business Analytics (This is the application of Big Data in different areas of Business and Corporate). Health Analytics (This is applicable in applications of the Analytics in Healthcare segment etc.), Retail Analytics (This is applicable in managing data and information in retail sectors) etc. Hence due to this, Big Data Analytics is applicable in diverse sectors viz. Transportation, Governance, Education, Commerce and Business, Manufacturing etc. There are different companies involved with the Big Data Analytics and among these primarily big giant MNCs are Microsoft Corporation, Teradata Corporation, SAP, EMC, HP, Dell.

Primarily only private organizations were involved with the Big Data Analytics but gradually Government bodies also implemented Big Data including associated systems and services.

Issues and Challenges: *The Power of ‘V’ and Big Data*

The applications of Big Data are rising in different are for its emergence and need. However Big Data is significant due to its characteristics such as (also refer fig: 3)—

Volume: It is actually the amount of data and including the similar content and form.

Variety: Data comes with various formats including normal text, image, audio, video content etc. and this nature of variety consider as important feature in complex data management.

Fig: 3 The Core Characteristics of Big Data

Variable: In data management, the variable is an important quantity as data is changeable. Different kind of inconsistency (or uniformity) has to be handled in Bigdata and data analytics.

Veracity (quality): In Bigdata quality of data is important to get the perfect accuracy and healthy

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deals with the applications. The quality is thus treated as veracity.

Velocity: Velocity is also important in data analytics in this context speed of the data is an important criterion.

Big Data Applications in Agriculture and Allied Sectors

Big Data and Analytics is very much important and valuable in developing better and smarter agricultural systems. The increasing amount of the populations, including demand for the food, climate change and so on lead the uses of Big Data and Analytics including other emerging technologies into agriculture directly and indirectly. Here IoT devices and other technologies can get the data or collect the data and thereafter Cloud Computing based systems helps in virtualization of the data but this large amount of generated data can be solved by the of Big Data and Analytics systems. The data related to the fields, soil, and plants aid, crops etc in real-time basis. Then expert or analyst integrates large amount of variety and complex data in different models and make them enable for the agriculture and allied sectors. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of Big Data and Analytics into Agriculture is 16.2%. The market size of Big Data and Analytics in agriculture is also increasing. In 2018 it was 585 USD million and it is expected it is to be reach at 1236 million by the end of 2023. There are many areas where Big Data and Analytics.

As a solution in the context of Growing Populations

Worldwide the populations are rising and this is become an important challenge in respect of the food productions. In this context various organizations, agricultural farms, industries, institutions etc. are moving well in respect of the better and productive agricultural foods, products and yields. With the help of Big data farmers and other stakeholders can get real time data on various aspects and areas such as rainfall patterns, water cycles, soil condition, crop condition, fertilizer requirements etc. and in this context it helps in productive agricultural foods.

This enables them to make smart decisions, such as what crops to plant for better profitability and when to harvest. The right decisions ultimately improve farm yields.Using mathematical modeling can be helpful in different activities and thus it helps in agro development in different context as well. The use of sensors for collecting data is worthy in data management and proper decision making.

Ethical Pesticides

Big Data Applications in the Agriculture is also helpful in the management and administration of the agricultural systems. Big Data with the AI based tools helpful in predicting regarding the uses of the pesticides. As pesticides is always harmful in the soil and agricultural products etc. Thushere Big Data and Analytics are helpful in identification of actual need of the pesticides,

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when to apply, how to apply etc. when, and by how much. Hence this is helpful in managing of pesticides uses and also ethically supports the human being and society as well.

Optimizing farm equipment

Big Data and Analytics is also helpful in the find out and optimizing farm and related equipments And for the big farms such kind of monitoring using Big Data is helpful and healthy in different context. This way Big Data and Analytics is applicable in other diverse areas as well as depicted in Fig: 4.

In Risk management

As far as Risk Management is concerned, Big Data and Analytics is also effective in find out the risk in agriculture including pre producing and post producing agricultural system. With this events like crop failure, and even improve feed efficiency and so on can be analyzed based on need and requirement. In post production activities like supply chain management, marketing management etc. Big Data and Analytics are effective.

Fig: 4-Agricultural Big Data impact in Agro Systems

In Food Safety & Prevention

In modern days agricultural systems Big Data and Analytics could be helpful in the activities such as Humidity, temperature and chemicals and this can lead the smart agricultural systems as well businesses in different context.

Equipment and Supply Chain management

In maintenance of equipment in order to reduce downtime and keep everything productive and to provide solutions of the equipment management and supply chain Big Data Analytics are very useful and solidly effective. Third of food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted every year according to the McKinsey. Big data can help achieve supply chain efficiencies with the help of tracking and optimizing delivery truck routes and for this other allied technologies also associated and useful viz.—

- Cloud Computing
- Internet of Things
- Robotics and AI etc.

And these are still growing in different context and ultimately helping in complex data management and solving agriculture related issues.

Environmental Data Science

Environmental Informatics requires different environmental activities such as energy, agriculture, forest management, water and oceanography and ecological systems. It helps by information-related activities with the help of technologies viz. environmental information management, environmental decision support, environmental geospatial services are also an essential beneficiary of Environmental Informatics. Among the most common technologies are used in this regard are GIS, Remote Sensing and GPS. Various branches and subjects even environmental chemistry and biochemistry are also significant users of Environmental Informatics. By the use of Environmental Informatics environmental phenomena viz. Atomic, molecular and macromolecular scales, etc. can also be effectively managed with its various stakeholders (Refer fig: 1).The following description about the Environmental Informatics is essential in this context.

- In designing, developing, modeling, implementing, evaluation of chemical, biological, environmental processes, Environmental Informatics directly and indirectly applicable.
- Websites related to the Environment, ecology, agriculture, etc. can be built with the help of Environmental Informatics.
- In Modeling of biotechnological systems, Environmental Informatics by its tools, technologies, etc. can be used effectively.
- Various kinds of multimedia tools, graphics, 3D tools, visualization systems of environmental and ecological management (with monitoring) can be possible with Environmental Informatics.

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Fig. 1: Depicted the Stakeholders of Environmental Informatics (Paul, PK, 2020)

Big Data is applicable in diverse areas of Environment and allied areas, and this is rising rapidly. It can be noted both in developed as well as developing countries as well (refer Fig: 3). Worldwide the data is generating numerously, and in 2017 alone, we generated more data than in the previous 5,000 years. It is applicable in analyzing the data and information and solutions as well. The Big Data applications in the Environment are helping in optimizing efficiency. Application of Big data to curb global warming is known as green data. It is an essential fact that 90% of the data having today on the online or internet base was generated only since the year 2016. Big Data is applied widely in medicine, agriculture, gambling and environmental protection. As far as environmental applications are concerned, few important are include (but not limited to)—

In Climate Change, Global Warming—

Big Data and Analytics is widely applicable in one of the current challenges of the modern world, i.e. Climate Change The application of big data to curb global warming is what is known as green data. Different countries have developed various projects on Big Data applications in Environment, and among them, Copernicus can be considered as the important one developed in Europe. This is based on satellite earth observation, and numerous data collected from the satellite here with the help of Big Data and Analytics are effectively managed.

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Fig. 2: Depicted different emerging technologies of Environmental Informatics (Paul, PK, 2020)

Copernicus is dedicated to providing information on various aspects and issues viz. water resource management, quality of the air, biodiversity, agriculture, forestry, fishing, etc. and in all these, Big Data technologies are widely applicable. As far as other international projects are concerned internationally, important are—

Aqueduct is another project responsible for the data collection and analysis of the water-related hazards, to get and analyze water quality and quantity. This is also applicable in making interactive risk maps to the public as well.

Global Forest Change This is also dedicated to forest management and applicable in deforestation by counting trees and here high-resolution satellite imagery is basically used for.

Danger Map, this international project is dedicated to determining pollution and based on data provided by the users.

In Smart Cities, Towns and Urban Planning—

It is worthy to note that worldwide the scenario of applications regarding the residence in cities and urban areas are changing and according to UN two-third of the world population by 2030 maybe live in the cities due to the general, more extensive and advanced benefits from the cities.

The environmental challenges and with Big Data it is resulting in the green data to solve the emerging problems. The uses of the analysis of big data to the creation of smarter and sustainable are increasing. And as far as Big Data and Analytics applications in smart cities, urbanization is concerned, few important are include—

- The GPS sensors are useful in waste management and also in the enhancement of the recycling pathways.
- In public transport planning location identification becomes possible, and here for future data management, Big Data and Analytics are widely applicable.

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- The satellite images, geospatial platforms, etc. can be nicely manageable with the help of Big Data and Analytics, and it may be helpful in natural disasters management.
- The Copenhagen Wheel is a bicycle wheel that collects data on air quality, noise levels and road conditions.
- The solar panel-based road is also emerging, and this is applicable that generate energy.
- There are different devices that are emerged which are responsible for pollution in the cities traffic flows, etc. and in all these Big Data and Analytics are effectively useful.

In Renewal Energy Management—

Big Data and Analytics is helpful in the competitiveness of renewable energies in fossil fuels. The Big Data is useful in the promotion of clean technologies by various means such as—

- In wind power management Big Data and Analytics is effectively useful by collecting the data and possible power to generate.
- In the efficiency of power stations related works, Big Data and Analytics is useful in different means and mode. Hence in photovoltaic power, this is effectively useful.
- Hydroelectric power also Big Data and Analytics is useful for the gathered data management and future uses.

Moreover these days, in general, electric bill meter also there are different changes can be noted and smart meters are evolved; many of such are well connected with the Internet of Things (IoT) and similar systems. Therefore the changes in statistics and data in this affairs can be managed effectively using Big Data and Analytics.

In Geographic Data Management—

In Geographic data management, including space, geospatial data management Big Data and Analytics are widely applicable. The areas where Big Data and Analytics are included but not limited to as follows—

- In simple cartographic naval navigation and generated data management.
- In geographic surveying, GIS-based data collection and development.
- In disaster and emergency management, Information Technology and Computing are widely used, and in such Big Data and Analytics are also using. Therefore it becomes important in environmental management as well. The GIS databases always engaged in Data Management and up-to-the-minute problem, and here Analytics can manage a huge amount of data generated.
- Satellite data are basically collected by the emerging tools such as GPS, Remote Sensing, GIS, etc. and in disaster management activities and here Big Data will further enhance its efficacy.

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Big Data is engaged in bringing different kinds of data management including air, water, and dry land, socio-economic data; therefore, useful in various Geo related data management effectively. Here the applications of other technologies can also be noted for better results.

Fig: 3Applications of Big Data and Analytics in broader Environmental Applications

In Planetary Monitoring—

Uses of technologies, especially Computing and Information Technologies, are significant in advanced planetary monitoring and here large-scale investment in Big Data infrastructure applicable in managing the environmental sector properly. In a program called CEMS (Climate and Environmental Monitoring from Space, large data sets are generated and here Big Data and Analytics useful in higher efficiency. However, here in addition to Big Data the Cloud Computing, IoT, etc. are also applicable and emerging rapidly. Governments of different countries are using various technologies in better and modern planetary monitoring, and here Big Data is effective, and in this regard, NASA was utilizing Big Data capture and storage for creating climate models, and it is to store as much as 32 petabytes of data/ information for modeling purposes. Different kind of data such as data sets, complex data and accumulated metadata are widely managed using Big Data and Analytics for better and healthy planetary monitoring.

In Agricultural Technological Management—

Agriculture is an integral part of the Environment and without it surviving is not possible. From agriculture, we get food products, and in the recent past, huge advancement of agriculture is

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noticeable, especially in methods, types and ways of farming and cultivation. Furthermore, in agricultural systems, information and computing technologies are also increasing rapidly for effective, advanced and productive agriculture. Due to the wider populations, various technologies are increasing. IT and Computing is applicable in the following activities—

- In pre-agricultural activities including in harvesting.
- In websites, web portals development related to the agriculture and allied areas.
- In design, development of the Agricultural Information Systems, Agricultural Information Networks, etc.
- In automated harvesting, spraying with water, chemical, etc.
- Remote and areal observations etc.

Therefore, Big Data Analytics is effectively applicable in a large amount of generated data from the agriculture and allied areas. Therefore, apart from the direct benefits of the agricultural products in is also indirectly helps in agricultural land and effectively using ground nutrients, managing water resources. Crowd sourced data, in conjunction with remote sensing, are widely applicable. According to some expert Big Data, and Analytics can help in providing mitigation and management tools for marginal landscapes already in use. Secondly in identifying the best uses for marginal landscapes in respect of agriculture etc.

In the field of Genetic Studies—

Big Data Analytics is widely and emerging other emerging areas which are indirectly associated with the Environment and Ecologies as well and among such one important is Genetic Engineering and Genetically Modified Technologies. This leads to the development of agricultural products and its growth, and as a result, it enhances the volume of the agricultural product as well. Hence in the monitoring of such agricultural products using technologies Big Data and Analytics become booming and growing rapidly.

To be a Socially Responsible Agent—

In another context, Big Data Analytics is also helping in social development, social promotion and welfare as well. In recent years, the corporate sectors are also involving in environmental affairs and for the promotion of the Environment and society as part of the corporate social responsibility. They are also using IT and emerging Big Data Management etc. and in this context, Green Data becomes essential and valuable for various affairs but among these important are—

- Robust optimization of energy management and resource utilization.
- Reducing carbon dioxide gas emissions from industrial and other sources.

Big data thus become an essential and powerful tool for monitoring and controlling sustainable

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development; directly and indirectly.

In the field of Citizen Science—

Big Data Analytics is widely applicable and enhancing the promotion of citizen science. The citizen sciences is involved with the development and promotion of the citizen and everyday people-related activities and in this context for the betterment of citizen and society as whole various technologies are widely useful and among these of the important is Big Data Analytics. The enhanced and broader uses of Big Data and Analytics can be helpful in fewer data management efforts, and indirectly it will reduce the environmental impact as well.

In the field of Anthropology & Archaeology—

Big Data Analytics is applicable in the field of anthropology and archaeology as well. Various studies reveal that these two fields are directly and indirectly associated. Collecting and managing data with various size, complexity, etc. can be effectively managed with the IT and especially emerging Big Data and Analytics. Cultural Studies is another important area where also Big Data and Analytics closely connected and useful.

In the areas of Environmental Conservation—

Big Data Analytics is effective and useful environmental conservation as well. In climate science and climate modeling, Big Data is useful in various affairs such as in conservation, sustainability and local environmental mitigation; therefore, here Big Data Analytics is effectively useful. Environmental NGOs are also collected various kinds of data from different stakeholders, and in this context, Big Data and Analytics are used in different means. Furthermore, Government bodies in determining policy regarding the ecology and environmental regulation and in such areas Big Data and Analytics are effectively useful. For example, the US, Dutch governments are engaged and also ensuring open data policy for Big Data analytics; therefore, here is the concern of environmental protection.

In the areas of Regional Planning—

Regional Planning is also an important issue in environmental engineering, and here for various areas, Information Technology and Computing are being used. The ecology, impact the environment, work for residents, etc. creates a huge amount of data, and here Big Data and Analytics are useful. There are wider areas of regional planning where Big Data and Analytics are effective and useful in the countries and areas; where not yet offered or started—

- In traffic and allied concern, Big Data and Analytics are widely and effectively useful viz. decision making on where to place new roads to be created, in crime

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management including where to focus law enforcement resources, etc.

- In addressing Health-related problems viz. in pollution, poverty, poor access solving Big Data Analytics useful.

Big Data thus helps in improving urban planning and resource allocation and led the “smart urban planning” etc. As urban and regional planning is a big concern and deals with various aspects therefore in multiple areas data are required viz. demographics, geographic information, employment-related, pollution, employment etc. and there are many other data and all such are required in better environmental practice; and here Big Data and Analytics may be widely useful and effective.

Complete and Sustainable Environmental Management—

Big Data Analytics is responsible for making green and sustainable agricultural development due to various concerns. With the advent of information technology, it is useful in broader areas and sectors, and in Environment also it is applicable and increasing. The growing data in the field of Environment and its variety lead the need of the Big Data and Analytics.

In healthy and better Decision Making—

The Big Data and Analytics helps in smoother presentation and reporting, delivering the environmental and allied data, and it helps in healthy and proper decision and policy development. Scientists and government deals with various environmental-related problems for a healthy future and in this context Big Data and Analytics widely useful and in this regard, other allied technology are also useful and associated with—

- Cloud Computing and Virtualization.
- Internet of Things.
- Robotics and AI.
- HCI and HCC etc

Therefore, Big Data Analytics is helping in environmental problem solving and helpful for the environmentalist, environmental experts, policymakers, government officers, etc.

Big Data in Environmental Sectors: Challenges & Issues

Big Data Analytics is applicable in various problem-solving in respect of Environment and ecology. And it worthy to note that like other emerging technology Big Data. Big Data and Analytics, Data Sciences, etc. has various concern and issues in respect of Environment, environmental engineering and management. However, among the issues, few important are include—

- Issues and concern of the methods for capturing data.

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- The capacity of data includes storing.
- Analyzing and visualization of the data.
- Searching, sharing as well as transferring data in various processes.
- In some contexts, the environmental data management aspects including the data security, privacy issues, etc. may be considered as important and valuable.
- The Environment is a broad concern, and there are various aspects, but interlinking can be considered as critical challenges.
- There are emerging concerns in the skill development in the field and also in Environment in respect of the big data management as well.

Proper policies, planning, regulation, etc. are highly welcome in the field of environmental engineering and particularly in data analytics and similar applications in the field of ecology and environment as well. Furthermore, due to the interaction and requirement of the Big Data and Analytics with Environmental Science/ Technology, etc. another nomenclature is developed that is called Environmental Data Science.

Conclusion

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